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Survival Analysis Of Chronic Kidney Disease Risk Factors: An Application Of Cox Regression Modeling

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ABSTRACT

Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) is a growing global health concern, driven largely by rising rates of diabetes, hypertension, and aging populations. Reliable identification of factors influencing CKD progression is essential for clinical decision-making and public health planning. Conventional modeling approaches such as logistic and Poisson regression do not account for time-to-event outcomes, potentially leading to biased estimates. This study applies the Cox Proportional Hazards model to evaluate key determinants of survival outcomes among CKD patients and compares its performance with logistic. Secondary data from 200 patients were obtained from Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital (ATBUTH), Bauchi, covering January 2023 to December 2023. CKD status served as the dependent variable, while Age, High Cholesterol, Blood Pressure, Diabetes Mellitus, Hypertension, and Coronary Artery Disease were examined as predictors. The Cox model showed that Diabetes Mellitus (HR = 2.42, $p < 0.001$) was the strongest predictor of CKD hazard, followed by Age (HR = 1.01, $p = 0.003$), while other covariates were not statistically significant. Proportional hazards assumptions were satisfied, and no influential cases were detected. Model comparison indicated that the Cox model (AIC = 200; BIC = 225) provided a superior fit relative to logistic model. The study concludes that survival-based modeling offers a more robust framework for CKD analysis and underscores the need for targeted diabetes prevention and age-related CKD monitoring strategies.

Keywords: Chronic Kidney Disease, Cox regression, Logistics regression, survival analysis, risk factors

INTRODUCTION

Kidneys are two bean-shaped organs; each kidney is about the size of a fist. Your kidneys filter extra water and wastes out of your blood and make urine. Kidney disease means your kidneys are damaged and can't filter blood the way they should. You are at greater risk for kidney disease if you have diabetes or high blood pressure. The most common statistical technique for modeling prevalence of Chronic Kidney

disease is logistic regression. Logistic regression analysis is one of the famous non-linear methods used to model the binary response variable based on ordinary explanatory variables. This method is particularly appropriate for models involving disease state (diseased/healthy), patient survival (alive/dead) and decision making (yes/no). So, it is widely used in studies in the health sciences (Bagley, 2001). Problems arise in classical logistic regression in situations such as Contravention of distribution assumptions (Bernoulli probability distribution for the binary response variable, uncorrelated explanatory variables, independency and identically distribution of error terms). Proportional Hazards regression is one of the good alternative to the logistic regression in modeling of disease. The Cox model is a regression technique for performing survival analyses in epidemiological and clinical research. This model estimates the hazard ratio (HR) of a given endpoint associated with a specific risk factor, which can be either a continuous variable like age and C-reactive protein level or a categorical variable like gender and diabetes mellitus. When the risk factor is a continuous variable, the Cox model provides the HR of the study endpoint associated with a predefined unit of increase in the independent variable (e.g., for every 1-year increase in age, 2 mg/L increase in C-reactive protein).

Logistic regression analysis is one of the famous non-linear methods used to model the binary response variable based on ordinary explanatory variables. This method is particularly appropriate for models involving disease states (diseased/healthy), patient survival (alive/dead) and decision making (yes/no). So, it is widely used in studies in the health sciences (Bagley, 2001). Khandpur *et al.* (2024), Investigated the Challenges in statistical modelling of predicting the prevalence of Chronic Kidney disease (CKD) by comparing the performances of Poisson model, Logistic model and Negative binomial, and their study recommended logistic regression as the best model for modelling prevalence of CKD. But on the other hand, the Logistic regression has the following weaknesses which would be a problem in modelling the CKD prevalence: The Logistic model assesses the odds of disease occurrence at a specific time point without considering the time of events. Likewise, logit does not account for censoring, which could lead to a biased estimate if the time of events is relevant. Therefore, this study intends to improve on their work by using a Cox regression model (Proportional hazards). The Cox model can analyze time until certain events occur which is often more informative than just the understanding the presence/absence of disease at a single point of time, as in the case of logistic. Likewise, the Cox regression can accommodate censored data, which is common in studies involving chronic disease where some patients may not have experienced the event of interest by the end of the study. So, the Cox model allowed incorporation of all available data more effectively. The study used secondary data on Chronic Kidney disease and its risk factors of (200) patients which were collected from January, 2023 to December, 2023, from Abubakar Tafawa University Teaching Hospital (ATBUTH) Bauchi, Bauchi State, Nigeria. The variables that were considered includes: Chronic Kidney disease (CKD) as the response variable, While High cholesterol (HC), Blood pressure (BP), Age (AG), Diabetes Mellitus (DM), Hypertension (HTN) and Coronary Artery Disease (CAD) are the categorical variables.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Logistic regression model.

Logistic regression is a popular modeling technique used to predict binary outcomes. The model is a linear model that captures the relationship between the input variables and the output variable (binary outcomes). The model uses a sigmoid function to convert the linear output into a binary outcome. Here are the steps for the development of a logistic regression model:

1. Data Preparation: We need to prepare the data by removing missing values, scaling the features, and handling categorical variables.
2. Feature Selection: We can use techniques like univariate analysis, correlation matrix, and feature importance to select the most relevant features for our model.
3. Model Selection: We need to split the data into training and validation sets and use techniques like cross-validation to tune the hyper parameters of the model.

4. Model Evaluation: We can evaluate the model's performance using metrics like accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and ROC-AUC.

The multiple binary logistics regression model is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \pi(X) &= \frac{\exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \dots + \beta_k X_k)}{1 + \exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \dots + \beta_k X_k)} & (1) \\ &= \frac{\exp(X\beta)}{1 + \exp(X\beta)} \\ &= \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-X\beta)} \end{aligned}$$

Where here π denotes a probability and not the irrational number 3.14...

π is the probability that an observation is in a specified category of the binary Y variable, generally called the "success probability". We notice that the model describes the probability of an event happening as a function of X variables. For instance, it may provide estimates of the probability that an older person has heart disease. With the logistic model, estimate of π from equations like the one above will always be between 0 and 1 the reasons are: The numerator $\exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 + \beta_{1x1} + \dots + \beta_{kxk})$ must be positive, because it is power of a positive value (e). The denominator of the model is (1+numerator), so the answer will always be less than 1. With one X variable, the theoretical model for π has an elongated "S" shape (or sigmoidal shape) with asymptotes at 0 and 1, although in sample estimate we may not see this "S" shape if the range of X variable is limited.

For a sample of size n, the likelihood for a binary logistic regression is given by:

$$L(\beta; y, X) = \prod_{i=1}^n \pi_i^{y_i} (1 - \pi_i)^{1-y_i} = \prod_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{\exp(X\beta)}{1 + \exp(X\beta)} \right)^{y_i} \left(\frac{1}{1 + \exp(X\beta)} \right)^{1-y_i} \quad (2)$$

The Cox's Proportional Hazard (Cox regression model)

The Cox Proportional Hazard (assuming hazard is constant for all patients) model is a semi parametric model in which the hazard function of the survival time is given by

$$h(t, \mathbf{X}) = h_0(t) \exp\left[\sum_{i=1}^p \beta_i X_i\right] = h_0(t) \exp(\boldsymbol{\beta}' \mathbf{X}) \quad (3)$$

$$h(t, \mathbf{X}) = h_0(t) \exp(\beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_p X_p) \quad (4)$$

where $h_0(t)$ is called the baseline hazard function, which is the hazard function for an individual for whom all the variables included in the model are zero., $\mathbf{X} = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_p)'$ is the values of vector of explanatory variables for a particular individual, and $\boldsymbol{\beta}' = (\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_p)$ is a vector of regression coefficients.

The corresponding survival functions are related as follows:

$$S(t, \mathbf{X}) = [s_0(t)] \exp\left[-\sum_{i=1}^p \beta_i X_i\right] \dots \dots \dots (5)$$

This model, also known as the Cox regression model, makes no assumptions about the form of $h_0(t)$ (non-parametric part of model) but assumes parametric form for the effect of the predictors on the hazard (parametric part of model). The model is therefore referred to as a semi-parametric model. The beauty of the Cox approach is that vagueness creates no problems for estimation.

Even though the baseline hazard is not specified, we can still get a good estimate for regression coefficients β hazard ratio, and adjusted hazard curves. The measure of effect is called hazard ratio. The hazard ratio of two individuals with different covariates x and x^* will be given by:

$$HR = \frac{\hat{h}(t, X^*)}{\hat{h}(t, X)} = \frac{\hat{h}_0(t) \exp(\sum_{i=1}^p \hat{\beta}_i X_i^*)}{\hat{h}_0(t) \exp(\sum_{i=1}^p \hat{\beta}_i X_i)} = \exp \left[\sum_{i=1}^p \hat{\beta}_i (X_i^* - X_i) \right] \dots \dots \dots (6)$$

For the sake of interpretation, we usually want $HR \geq 1$ i.e., $\hat{h}(t, X^*) \geq \hat{h}(t, X)$

This hazard ratio is time-independent, which is why this is called the proportional hazards model.

Model Specification

Taking CKD as the dependent variable and while Age (AG), high cholesterol (HC), Blood pressure (BP), Diabetes Mellitus (DM), Hypertension (HTN) and Anemia (A) as independent determinant factors, and based on the fact that the ratio of the hazards for any two individuals i and j is constant over time the expected model will assume the form:

$$S(t, X) = [S_0(t)]^{\exp(\beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4)} \dots \dots \dots (7)$$

Where β'_i s are estimated coefficients of the regression model such that $\beta_o = \ln(S_o)$, is the baseline constant for the regression model.

$\beta =$ relative risk, $X_1 =$ Age (AG), $X_2 =$ High cholestorol (HC)
 $=$ Blood pressure (BP), $X_4 =$ Diabetes Milletus (DM), X_5
 $=$ hpertension (HTN) and $X_6 =$ Anemia (A)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1: Case Processing Summary for Proportional Hazards (Cox) regression

Cases	Event	N	Percentage
Cases available in analysis	Event ^a	106	53%
	Censored	94	47%
	Total	200	100%
Cases dropped	Cases with missing values	0	0%
	Cases with negative time	0	0%
	Censored cases before the earliest event in a stratum	0	0%
	Total	0	0%
Total		200	100%

a. Dependent Variable: Duration

Table 2: Proportional Hazard (Cox) regression results of CKD data.

Variables	Coefficient	HR	Z	Pr(> z)
HC	0.1866	1.2051	0.735	0.4621
BP	0.0007	1.0007	0.275	0.7831
AG	0.0135	1.0136	3.012	0.00268 **
DM	0.8826	2.4172	4.236	2.28e-05 ***
HTN	-0.0642	0.9378	-0.272	0.7859
CAD	-0.1175	0.8891	-0.505	0.6139
AIC	200			
BIC	225			

Source: Authors' computation aided by R package v4.4.1. Note: (**) and (***) denote significance at 5% and 1% respectively.

Table 2 shows the result of the Proportional Hazard (Cox) regression for Chronic Kidney disease (CKD) and its covariates in terms of Coefficients (β s), Hazard ratio (HR), Wald test (Z) and its p -values (Pr (>|z|)) respectively. From the result of cox regression obtained in the table 2 above, the coefficient (β) represents the change in the log of the hazard for each unit increase in the covariate, while the hazard ratio (HR) represents the corresponding multiplicative change in the hazard. With the relationship $HR = e^{\beta}$, the HR has the following conditions; $\beta > 1$ hazard increases (HR>1), $\beta < 1$ hazard decreases (HR < 1) and as $\beta \approx 0$ little or no effect (HR \approx 1). Therefore, the result showed that after adjusting for all covariates, Diabetes mellitus (DM) emerged as the strongest predictor of hazard, having β (0.0883) with a corresponding Z statistic of 4.24 ($p < 0.001$ which far < 0.05) indicating a highly significant effect. The hazard ratio (HR = 2.42 shows that a diabetes mellitus (DM) patients had approximately 2.4 times higher hazard of experiencing death due to Chronic Kidney disease (CKD) compared with non-diabetic mellitus patients.

In the same vain, Age (AG) covariate was also found to be a significant predictor for chronic kidney disease (CKD), with a regression coefficient (β) (0.014) and a Z statistic of 3.01 ($p = 0.003$). The hazard ratio (HR = 1.01) indicates that each 1-unit increase in age is associated with a 1.36% increase in hazard for patients leaving with chronic kidney disease, representing a modest but statistically meaningful effect. Consequently, the result also showed that high cholesterol (HC) with ($\beta = 0.187$, HR = 1.21, Z = 0.736, $p = 0.462$), Blood pressure (BP) ($\beta = 0.001$, HR = 1.00, Z = 0.275, $p = 0.783$), Hypertension (HTN) ($\beta = -0.064$, HR = 0.94, Z = -0.272, $p = 0.786$), and coronary artery disease (CAD) ($\beta = -0.118$, HR = 0.89, Z = -0.505, $p = 0.614$) were not statistically significant predictors of hazard in this model. Therefore, results of the study indicated that diabetes mellitus is the most important covariate predictor of hazard for chronic kidney disease (CKD), followed by age (AG) which contributed a smaller but statistically significant effect. While other risk factors did not show significant associations with hazard for chronic kidney disease.

Table 3: Proportional Hazard (Cox) regression results of CKD data.

Variables	HR	LCI(95%)	UCI(95%)
HC	1.2051	0.7329	1.982
BP	1.0007	0.9954	1.006
AG	1.0136	1.0001	1.027
DM	2.4172	1.6068	3.636
HTN	0.9378	0.5900	1.491
CAD	0.8891	0.5633	1.403
Concordance	0.626		
Likelihood (r.t)	27.32		
Wald test	26.96		
Score (logrank)	28.89		

Source: Authors' computation aided by R package v4.4.1

Table 3 presents the cox proportional hazard regression results for CKD data. It can be observed that the hazard ratios (HRs) are reported alongside their 95% confidence intervals (LCI-UCI), which provide a range within which the true effect is expected to fall. A covariate is said to be statistically significant if the confidence interval does not include unity (1.0). It can be seen from the results presented in table 3 that diabetes mellitus (DM) was found to be the strongest predictor, with patients having more than twice the hazard of adverse outcomes compared to non-diabetic patients (HR = 2.42, 95% CI: 1.6 – 3.64). Since both the lower and upper limits of the confidence interval exceed 1, this association is statistically significant. Age (AG) was also found to be a modest but with significant effect, with each unit increase associated with a 1.3% higher hazard (HR = 1.01, 95% CI: 1.00 – 1.03). while, High cholesterol (HC: 0.73 – 1.98), Blood pressure (BP: 0.99 – 1.01), Hypertension (HTN: 0.59 – 1.49), and Coronary artery disease (CAD: 0.56 – 1.40) all crossed unity, indicating that these covariates were not statistically significant predictors of hazard in this model. Furthermore, the global measures of the model performance further support the reliability of these findings. The concordance statistic was found to be 0.626 indicating a moderate ability of the model to discriminate between patients with higher versus lower risk. In addition, the likelihood ratio test ($X^2 = 27.32$), Wald test ($X^2 = 26.96$), and log-rank test ($X^2 = 28.89$) were all statistically significant, confirming that the overall model provides a good fit and that, collectively, the included variables contribute meaningfully to explaining variations in hazard of the CKD and its covariates.

Diagnostics for the Proportional Hazard (Cox) model result for CKD data

The Cox proportional hazards model makes several assumptions. Thus, it is important to assess whether a fitted Cox regression model adequately describes the data.

Testing for Proportional Hazards assumption in the CKD model

Table 4: Statistical test for checking PH assumptions

Methods	chisq	df	P
HC	0.700	1	0.403
BP	2.830	1	0.093
AG	0.709	1	0.400
DM	2.754	1	0.097
HTN	0.657	1	0.418
CAD	0.753	1	0.385
GLOBAL	6.947	6	0.326

Source: Authors' computation aided by R package v4.4.1

Table 4 presents the results of the statistical test for the proportional hazards (PH) assumption in the Cox regression model of chronic Kidney disease (CKD) data. The proportional hazards assumption requires that the hazard ratios for respective covariates remain constant over time, and this can be evaluated through the Schoenfeld residuals test. In this test, a p-value greater than 0.05 indicates that the assumption is not violated, whereas a p-value less than 0.05 suggest violation.

So, looking at our p-values of covariates from table 4, HC ($p = 0.403$), BP ($p = 0.093$), AG ($p = 0.400$), DM ($p = 0.097$), HTN ($p = 0.418$), and CAD ($p = 0.385$) have p-values greater than 0.05. And this implies that none of these variables violated the proportional hazards assumption. Moreover, the global test ($p = 0.326$) also exceeds the 0.05 threshold. This global statistic confirms that the model as a whole meets the proportional hazards assumption. In other words, there is no evidence to suggest time-dependent effects of the covariates on the hazard function, and the Cox regression model is valid for the CKD dataset.

Global Schoenfeld Test p: 0.3258

Figure 1: Scale Schoenfeld Residual Plots

Source: Authors' computation aided by R package v4.4.1

The figure 1 above shows the Schoenfeld residual test, which was also used to assess the proportional hazards assumption of the Cox regression model. It can be noticed from the figure, that the global test yielded a p-value of 0.326, indicating that the proportional hazards assumption was not violated at the 5% level of significance. By examining the individual Schoenfeld residual plots for covariates (HC, BP, AG, DM, HTN and CAD) revealed no clear time-dependent trends, as the smoothed lines fluctuated around zero without systematic deviation. Thus, both the global and individual test confirmed that the proportional hazards assumption of the Cox regression model was adequately met.

Testing for Influential Observations in the CKD PH model

Figure 2: Index dbeta Plots for Cox model

Source: Authors’ computation aided by R package v4.4.1

Figure 2 displays the dfbeta index plots for the covariates included in the Cox regression model, namely Diabetes mellitus (DM), Age (AG), High cholesterol (HC), Blood pressure (BP), Hypertension (HTN), and Coronary artery disease (CAD). The dfbeta statistic evaluates how much each observation influences the regression coefficient of a given covariate when it is omitted from the model. It can observe that for all the covariates, the dfbeta values are centered around zero with the majority of points clustering close to the horizontal axis.

- **DM (Diabetes mellitus):** The values fluctuate narrowly around zero without extreme deviations, indicating no undue influence of single observations on the coefficient for DM.

- **AG (Age):** The spread of dfbeta values is minimal and symmetric around zero, implying that the effect of age is consistently estimated without the presence of influential outliers.
- **HC (High cholesterol):** The observations are tightly distributed near zero, showing that the coefficient for HC remains stable across cases.
- **BP (Blood pressure):** A similar narrow band around zero is observed, signifying a reliable coefficient estimate for BP.
- **HTN (Hypertension):** The dfbeta values demonstrate minimal variation, with no influential cases detected for hypertension.
- **CAD (Coronary artery disease):** The values remain symmetrically scattered around zero, implying the absence of influential observations affecting CAD.

Therefore, we can conclude that none of the covariates exhibit dfbeta values that stand out as potential outliers or highly influential points. So, this indicates that the Cox regression model is not unduly affected by individual observations, and the estimated effects of the covariates are stable and reliable. Thus, the assumption regarding the absence of influential observation is satisfied for all the covariates in the model.

Table 5: Case Processing Summary for logistic regression

Unweighted Cases	Event	N	Percentage
Selected cases	Included in Analysis	200	100%
	Missing Cases		
	Total	0	100%
		200	100%
Unselected Cases		0	0%
		200	100%
Total			

Table 6: Dependent Variable Encoding

Original value	Internal value
ALIVE	0
DEAD	1

Table 7: Ordinary logistic regression results of CKD data.

Variables	Coefficient	S.E	z value	Pr(> z)
(Intercept)	-2.6981	0.9061	-2.978	0.00290 **
HC	0.3251	0.3981	0.816	0.41425
BP	0.0053	0.0044	1.182	0.23701
AG	0.0317	0.0106	3.003	0.0488 *
DM	2.1309	0.4040	5.275	1.33e-07 ***
HTN	0.0313	0.3852	0.081	0.93518
CAD	-0.2918	0.3837	-0.761	0.44692
AIC	235			
BIC	258			

Source: Authors' computation aided by R package v4.4.1. Note: (**) and (***) denote significance at 5% and 1% respectively.

Table 7 presents the results of ordinary logistic regression model for CKD data and its determinant. The coefficient for HC was found to be 0.3251, indicating that every –unit increase in High cholesterol (HC), the log-odds of developing CKD increase by 32.5% holding other variables constant. The corresponding z-value of 0.816 and p-value of 0.414 demonstrate that HC is not statistically significant predictor of CKD data. Looking at the second variable BP the coefficient is 0.0053 shows that higher blood pressure is positively associated with the odds of CKD. The z-value of 1.182 and p-value of 0.23701 indicate that BP is not a significant predictor of CKD. For Age (AG) the coefficient was found to

be 0.0317, indicating that for every one-year increase age, the log-odds of escalating CKD increases by 3.2%, holding other variables constant. The corresponding z-value of 3.003 and p-value of 0.0488 demonstrate that age is statistically significant predictor of CKD. This implies that increasing age significantly elevates risk of CKD accordingly. Furthermore, the coefficients of Diabetes Mellitus was found to be 2.1309 indicating that diabetic patients have higher log-odds of developing CKD compared to non-diabetics. The z-value of 5.275 and p-value of 1.33e-07 confirm that diabetes mellitus is a significant predictor of CKD. This is consistent with the known role of diabetes as a leading risk factor of kidney disease.

The coefficient of hypertension (HTN) is 0.0313 implying that 1-unit increase in HTN increases the risk of CKD by 3.13%. The z-value of 0.081 and p-value of 0.93518 indicate that HTN variable is not significant of variable of escalating the CKD. Finally, the coefficient of Coronary artery diseases was found to be -0.2918 indicating 1-unit increase in CAD decreases the CKD by 29.18%. And it was found to be non-significant risk factor variable for CKD.

Table 9: Comparing the performances of Cox and Logistic regression Models in modeling the prevalence of Chronic Kidney disease (CKD)

Methods	AIC	BIC
Cox	200	225
Logistic	235	258

Source: Authors' computation aided by R package v 4.4.1

The goodness of fit of the Cox proportional hazards and logistic regression models was evaluated using Akaike's Information Criteria (AIC) and Bayesian Information Criteria (BIC). As shown in Table 9, the Cox regression model yielded the lowest AIC (200) and BIC (225) compared to the Logistic (AIC = 235; BIC = 258). The results revealed that the Cox regression provided the best result balance between model complexity and explanatory power for the survival data of CKD patients. The Cox model outperformed the other models because of its capacity to incorporate time-to-event information, which logistic cannot adequately capture. The logistic model is useful for binary event outcomes, ignoring survival time.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, we conclude that across the two models, Diabetes mellitus consistently emerged as the strongest and most significant predictor of adverse effect of CKD outcomes. While age was also found to be an important predictor with little effect but significant. Other risk factors did not show significant statistical effects but remain clinically relevant. The study also concludes that Cox regression model found to be most robust and reliable approach for survival analysis of CKD data, as it incorporates time-to-event information and offers superior model fit. While logistic may still serve as complementary tools in situations where outcomes are strictly binary. Finally, the study recommended that Cox regression model should be adopted in analyzing CKD survival data, giving its robustness and superior model performance compared to logistic; Health policymakers and practitioners should prioritize diabetes prevention and management programs, as diabetes was shown to be the strongest predictor of CKD outcomes and special approach to patients' care should be adopted, ensuring that factors such as blood pressure, cholesterol, and cardiovascular conditions are addressed, even though they were found to be non-significant in the study.

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